

Emerging trend of e-commerce in Pakistan Critical Issues, Predication and Challenges

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Abstract: The Internet has transformed the way businesses do business in the 21st century, has changed the face and advancement of businesses and is an indispensable opportunity for operating on a digital platform. Through these digital platforms, companies can find new sources of competitive advantage. Therefore, it is more integrated into the e-commerce channel. The advancement of telecommunication technology has promoted the development of the e-commerce environment around the world. With the development of e-commerce, it has become an essential tool for people in developed countries. But in developing countries like Pakistan, the growth and development of e-commerce is slow. E-commerce privacy, security and trust are key areas, which have a negative and hostile impact on the development and expansion of e-commerce in Pakistan. In this study, the interpretation of customer privacy, security and trust will be discussed, highlighting the importance of privacy issues, appropriate security measures and the development of trust. The literature used in this research underscores the need to improve privacy and security measures and the importance of Pakistani customers' trust in building relationships with e-commerce providers. There are few workarounds to solve these problems.

Keywords: *Privacy, Security, Issues, Trends, Trust, E-commerce, Pakistan.*

INTRODUCTIN: The use of the Internet is expanding rapidly and continuously, now people can easily access the Internet due to its wider availability (Desai, Richards and Desai, 2003), the development of globalization and information technology has opened up new avenues. For organizations and entrepreneurs to develop and deliver products and services efficiently in a short time (Imtiaz & Kim, 2019), the development of information and communication technology (ICT) provides customers with a broader interactive experience and Better (Chien-Ta Ho & Oh, 2009) The combination of technology and business has led to the rise of e-commerce, in which manufacturers, distributors and consumers build connections via the Internet to buy and sell products in a wide variety of environments. End the world Business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) transactions are the two most popular types of e-commerce contributing to e-commerce technology (Chan & Kwok, 2001; Gupta & Hammond, 2005), according to Turban, Outland, King, Lee, Liang and Turban (2017) E-commerce is the process of selling, buying and buying products, services and information over the Internet. Studies have shown that e-commerce has changed the way we do business (Makame, Kang and Park, 2014) and has become a major contributor to the economic growth of countries (Schware, 2005), unlike trade. Traditionally, e-commerce does not allow real interactions between buyers and sellers. But this fact poses many problems, including law, technology, privacy, security and trust (Oreku & Li, 2005). It is a perception of the risks of e-commerce development in Pakistan. In e-commerce, privacy, security, and trust are key factors for e-commerce organizations and consumers (Featherman, Miyazaki and Sprott, 2010). Online security is the foundation for the development of trust (Panula, 2017). Reliability is an essential element in e-commerce. Customers are more concerned with the opposite level of trust (Hallikainen & Laukkanen, 2018). Most customers are dissatisfied with today's e-commerce strategy regarding privacy, security, and trust. These insecurities are driving economic development. Online security breaches are a major threat to the development of the global economy. It can be seen that the growth of e-commerce is increasing and, as a result, issues, especially

those related to privacy and security, have been surprisingly considered in recent years. Privacy and security related issues are the main reasons why customers leave online shopping (Nilashi, Bagherifard, Ibrahim, Janahmadi and Barisami, 2011; Udo, 2001; Yenisey, Ozok and Salvendy, 2005). Security is an important factor in expanding the level of cooperation with customers. Research has shown that issues related to privacy and security in e-commerce are effectively linked to trust and repeat purchase intent (Chiu, Wang, Fang and Huang, 2014; Sharma and Yetton, 2003). High privacy is a positive factor for trust (Wu, Huang, Yen, and Popova, 2012). A high level of privacy and security reduces fraud and risk, and ultimately increases your willingness to buy. Of customers (Miyazaki & Fernandez, 2000) Trust is also an important factor in online transactions. Every customer thinks of their trust when doing online transactions. We can't say that a supplier's website can build a trusting relationship right from the start. But when customers re-purchase from the same supplier, the establishment of the company can evolve over time (Sisson, 2000). The growth and development of e-commerce in Pakistan. Hence, this research is based on literature, emphasizing the need for increased privacy and security measures, as well as the importance of customer trust in developing online relationships. There are also a few potential solutions to address these issues. The privacy, security and trust factors in e-commerce are important to customers, companies, and regulators.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Privacy: From a customer perspective, the perception of personal information security risks is a major concern in e-commerce (Miyazaki & Fernandez, 2001). Customers are increasingly concerned about the security of their personal information as many customers are reluctant. To provide personal information when doing online transactions (Metzger, 2004) when doing e-commerce transactions, certain personal information such as an address, credit card number and bank account is required. People think a lot about their privacy, which is why they are more concerned when trying to shop online. Sometimes they tend to withdraw their transactions for fear of personal information being leaked

(Boritz, No, & Sundarraj, 2008; Metzger, 2004) .This hinders the development of e-commerce and affects sales and profits of E-commerce organization E-commerce organizations can create a positive image in consumers' minds and increase their trust by keeping consumer information and personal information protected and respected when doing online transactions. If a supplier's website fails to establish credibility and security measures for their personal and information data, the corporate image will be negatively impacted and they eventually lose trust. From the consumer (LeGresley, 2004) business environment Data acquisition using digital systems and new processing techniques for data mining is easier. Ecommerce sites are collecting large amounts of information related to customer preferences, how they buy it, and what they search for in large quantities. Business analysts are using this information to customize the customer experience and improve the website. E-commerce organizations collect personal information to provide better services. But this information may be misused. G. By disclosure to third parties (Boritz & No, 2011) Pakistani consumers are increasingly concerned about their personal information. This is why Pakistani consumers are restricted from shopping online. Despite the size of the Pakistani market, it is limited to online purchases (Baig, Raza and Farooq, 2011). In order to maintain privacy in e-commerce businesses, a complete and secure system is required. Privacy is a major concern for Pakistani consumers as most purchases are made via cash on delivery rather than credit card. A key factor limiting online transactions in Pakistan is the use of cash on delivery (Sheikh & Basti, 2015), Hussein, Wallace, Tassabeji and Khan (2007) addressed issues related to payment methods in Pakistan and found that They don't like using credit cards to make purchases.90% of e-commerce transactions are done through cash on delivery (PTA, 2017).

Security: Security is a key component of e-commerce development (Tian & Dai, 2010). Scholars believe that good security can increase trust and ultimately increase the adoption and use of e-commerce. But only in Pakistan But also around the world According to Udo's definition (2001), security can be defined as "Data protection to prevent accidental or intentional disclosure of information to unauthorized persons or unauthorized modification or destruction." Confidentiality, assertion, waiver and possibility (Oreku & Li, 2005; Wang, Zou, & Zhang, 2010) Concerns about security risks have become a global concern. When the system fails to protect customers' confidential information, the viability of the system is threatened (Kesh, Ramanujan and Nerur, 2002). As consumer trust decreases, e-commerce is hindered. Hence, it represents a huge threat to diffusion and universal development. For security reasons, consumers do not shop online (Udo, 2001). The explanation behind the high security risk is associated with flaws in e-commerce framework laws and regulations (Meng, 2008). E-Commerce and E-Commerce have expanded their illegal exploitation measures to the data framework that was initially considered secure (Gupta & Hammond, 2005). Ecommerce is completely dependent on IT, which means that future ecommerce developments will rely on security. Of IT and Risk Management Effectively (Holbein & Gaugler, 1999) No matter what kind of enterprise security software is trying to procure, this

success cannot be guaranteed as there are many variables that affect the flow of information and Internet safety To build consumer trust, there must be a systematic change. The e-commerce security strategy involves two aspects: protecting the integrity of business networks and internal systems, and the security awareness of transactions between customers and organizations. E-commerce organizations must continually review this issue and provide appropriate countermeasures. Security measures must be taken so as not to interfere with or discourage the projected ecommerce operations.

Trust: Regarding ecommerce, there are different studies based on credibility research. But the literature on trust reviews suggests that there is no general definition of trust (Chen & Dhillon, 2003). Trusts are defined in many forms, such as economics, information systems (IS), and social networks. But an e-commerce trust represents a moderator's expectation of caregiver behavior and motivation (Iqbal, Hunjra and Rehman, 2012). The trust provides prudent insights to a successful eCommerce transaction (Chen & Li Consumer trust in e-commerce organizations is an important part of the online shopping choice (Iqbal et al., 2012; Jarvenpaa and Todd, 1996; Reichheld & Scheffer, 2000; Lee, 2019; Kim, 2018)). Consumers generally do not buy online from unreliable suppliers (Kang & Moon, 2017) .In e-commerce, trust is an important issue because in online transactions, customers do not have one-to-one contact with the supplier. Trust is a psychological alternative to reducing the complexity and insecurity of e-commerce transactions. It is very important to study trust to understand whether customers are involved in e-commerce activities (Gupta & Dubey, 2016) .Amazon and e-bay are e-commerce giants. Increasing the trust of prospective customers (Khan, Yousaf, Mian and Nawaz, 2013) in Pakistan, the use of e-commerce is immature and the biggest obstacle is the lack of trust. First of all, people tend to abandon their purchasing decisions without looking at the product. Unless it's a brand they trust and have used it many times in the past. E-commerce reviews show that there are three measures of trust: kindness, competence, and honesty. (Bhattacharjee, 2006; Clemons et al., 2013). Compassion rests in an organization's desire to safeguard the interests of consumers and strive for them to benefit. Integrity in e-commerce means that online sellers have to continually strive to satisfy their buyers (Chen & Dhillon, 2003). Competence means e-commerce has the right talent and capabilities to meet various needs. Of consumers (Gefen, 2002), a lack of trust in e-commerce organizations is a major obstacle to online shopping (Gefen, 2002; Hoffman, Novak and Chatterjee, 1995). Trust is very important in e-commerce and plays a role. It's important to realize the real benefits of ecommerce. Reliability is essential to ensure that ecommerce service providers and users get the desired performance. Understanding building trust is the first step (Kini & Choobineh, 1998). Trust impacts consumers' attitudes towards online shopping (Lee & Lin, 2005). Benefits from building trust From a corporate perspective, they will benefit more in terms of reliability and loyalty. From the customer's point of view, they can strive to make more purchases online (Habibi and Hajati, 2015). Reliability is a key indicator of first online purchases and repeat purchases (Fang, Qureshi, Sun, McCole, Ramsey and Lim, 2014).

E-COMMERCE IN PAKISTAN: E-commerce is the most essential driver of digital Pakistan (PTA, 2017). By 2000, Pakistan faced many obstacles in terms of lack of e-commerce law and lack of appropriate infra-structure, only 1% of the whole population had internet connections but the numbers of internet users are growing year by year in Pakistan and it has reached to 22. 2% of population in 2018 (Internet World Stats, 2018). The survey report on the internet usage and population stats is shown in Table 1. In developed countries, e-commerce has grown enormously. In Pakistan like other developing nations of the world, the internet has just been set up and acknowledged warmly (Khan et al., 2013) but the development and growth of e-commerce remain low in Pakistan contrasting to the developed countries (Khan & Bawden, 2005). The government of Pakistan is currently truly promoting the development and advancement in e-commerce. Now Pakistan has an e-commerce law and internet users are also growing (Blythe, 2006). Economists are suggesting that the spread of new information and communication technologies (ICT's) in the country can have a noteworthy effect on economic growth. Pakistan has enormous potential for e-commerce development and growth because of its high populace and a high proportion of youngsters in society (Agren & Barbutiu, 2018). Regardless of ICT development in Pakistan, the adoption of e-commerce stays on a basic level (Moomal & Masrom, 2015; Sohaib & Kang, 2014) but the country is now increasingly shifting towards digitalization and facing some good or bad experiences through this process. Good experiences in terms of widely accepted internet and low-cost broadband packages and bad experiences in terms of challenges with regards to ICT utilization and difficulties in payments. Regardless of the reality, citizens are likewise beginning to know that business on the internet gives numerous advantages

(Moomal & Masrom, 2015; Qureshi, Fatima, & Sarwar, 2014) but the numerous restraints also exist in Pakistan and this is the reason the consumer's online buying rate is low. The mentalities of individuals towards buying online are diverse in Pakistan. Many people use the internet but still there are some reasons by which consumers are hesitant to purchase online. Trust found as a critical factor (Nazir, Tayyab, Sajid, ur Rashid, & Javed, 2012). Despite the high rate of e-commerce activities, trust has remained the biggest factor that restricts Pakistani consumers to buy online. According to Zeb (2017), security is the main reason that hinders e-commerce growth in Pakistan. Chaudary, Rehman and Nisar (2014) conducted a study on factors influencing the acceptance of online shopping in Pakistan and discussed privacy as a barrier to the development of e-commerce in Pakistan. Entrepreneurs have launched the e-commerce initiatives for consumers that have been success stories such as daraz. pk, olx. com, homeshopping. pk. It is estimated that the size of Pakistan e-commerce market falls between US\$ 60 ~ 100 million (2015) and expected to grow up to the US \$1 billion by 2020. Pakistan is generally a cash-driven economy as the number of debit/credit cardholders is small and m-wallet accounts are also very low due to which more than 95% of the e-commerce transactions are done by cash on delivery system. Pakistan is also making good progress on the business to business (B2B) front as the software industry aims to achieve the goal of US \$5 billion export mark by the year 2020. Furthermore, the IT industry has various medium-sized IT firms earning nearly \$530 million, mainly in software development and service outsourcing. However, Pakistan's share in the global IT sales is just US\$ 2.8 billion out of the global US \$3.2 trillion global markets (PTA, 2017).

Table 1. Internet usage and population statistics in Pakistan

Years	Users	Population	Percentage (%)	Usage source
2000	133,900	163,985,373	0.1	ITU*
2006	12,000,000	167,806,831	7.2	ITU
2009	18,500,000	174,578,558	10.6	ITU
2010	18,500,000	177,276,594	10.4	ITU
2016	34,342,400	192,758,348	17.8	ITU
2018	44,608,065	200,813,818	22.2	IWS**

POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS:

For Privacy: The online privacy is essential for e-commerce customers (Jeon & Kwon, 2016). The frequent headlines of security breaches and inappropriate data use by major companies have made consumers more vigilant than ever about their privacy protection. Posting a privacy policy statement on your e-commerce site is a significant way to earn their trust. However, an effective privacy policy is not just a disclosure statement. The possible solution to privacy issues could incorporate by developing more customized privacy activities (Boritz, et al., 2008). Presenting a P3P (platform for privacy preferences project) framework into organization's websites will show customers that how the website

gathers, handles, and uses their private information is likewise advisable (Yin, Li, & Sun, 2007). The goal of P3P is to enable WWW sites to express their privacy practices and users to exercise preferences over those practices. The other possible solution is a TRUSTe program which addresses the privacy concerns of consumers and WWW sites. The TRUSTe program enables companies to develop privacy statements that reflect the information gathering and dissemination practices of their site. Its goal is to provide online consumers with control over their personal information. The ongoing exploration recommends that when performing e-services, privacy risks can be affected by

the corporate reliability of the vendor and the ease of use of service (Featherman, et al., 2010).

For Security: Make customers satisfied, loyal and build a high degree of trust; security measures should be improved. Most organizations do not fully focus on security but focus on infrastructure. These organizations are considered cost-driven rather than value-driven (Holbein & Gaugler, 1999; Oreku & Li, 2005). This kind of thinking should be changed, and e-commerce service providers should focus on considering customer needs and find ways to enhance and modify security measures. For software developers, it is very important to develop software that can provide and improve security measures. G. Digital signature is used as a means to verify the integrity and enhancement of data (Marchany & Tront, 2002; Oreku & Li, 2005). In order for any online business to succeed, the security issues in e-commerce, such as integrity, identity verification and non-repudiation, must be effectively dealt with. Data integrity is the guarantee that the transmitted data is consistent and correct. Identity verification is a means by which both parties to an online transaction can be confident that they are their true identities. Non-repudiation is the idea that neither party can disagree with the actual transaction. In addition, holding seminars to guide and make customers aware of security-related issues is also an important part of the security implementation process (Marchany & Tront, 2002). Therefore, we can look at the vigorous development of online business security together, and we must conduct a comprehensive study from 24 perspectives, and focus on the organization's guarantees and customer needs.

For Trust: Lack of consumer trust is one of the biggest obstacles to e-commerce development and growth. With the development of technology, trust has become a currency of communication, not just buying a product. An innovative shopping experience requires deep relationships with customers. Reliability is a key factor that influences customers' purchasing decisions. There is a relationship between trust and customer purchasing decisions. If customers trust your ecommerce site or service provider, they'll buy more. In order to build customer trust with ecommerce providers, online stores must improve their sites to influence potential customers so they can make good purchasing decisions. There are good ways to build customer trust: (1) by showing a security seal and adding a trust badge (2) using a trustworthy payment gateway (3) showing real reviews of Real and honest customers (4) get customers from Service Provider Request (5) Processing of returns by displaying actual photos or videos, Shipping Policy and Refund Procedures, etc. (5) As the customer values the quality of the product (Leibowitz , 2016) Here's how to build trust. But there are other ways.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION: Even though e-commerce is an emerging market in Pakistan, it is likely to face various challenges. Although many of these challenges are providing scope for innovation, thus driving the market forward. Pakistani market is fragmented with poor logistics infrastructure. Issue of mistrust prevails among the customers regarding the security and privacy of their personal information like credit cards, phone numbers, and home addresses, etc. Also, people lack confidence with the newly emerging

companies in the online market which needs to be taken into account by the government authorities. An analysis of the effect of privacy, security, and trust related issues on the growth and development of e-commerce uncovers that with the quick development and extension of e-commerce; privacy, security, and trust related issues are expanding among consumers. This study reveals that how Pakistani customers' perception of potential threats and risks to the privacy, security, and trust influences their purchase decision. Gefen and Straub (2003) suggest that trust is a major concern in making online purchase. In the absence of physical interaction with the seller, the risk to the buyer increases. Ha and Stoel (2009) support this argument by indicating that the importance of trust increases the online shopping. This also holds true for Pakistan. Due to the lack of trust, the threat of revelation of privacy and improper security measures, many Pakistani customers deny purchasing online. For the development and growth of e-commerce in Pakistan, e-commerce organizations need to comprehend these necessities by developing that kind of security systems, frameworks, techniques that would guarantee the secure transaction between vendors and buyers. This progression would ensure the expanded customer base and ultimately ascertain to be exceptionally productive and profitable. This study presented the three issues in the Pakistani e-commerce environment: privacy, security, and trust. These three issues are the key causes to be discussed to facilitate e-commerce growth in Pakistan. This study discusses the trust related issues and the reasons behind these issues, its effects on the development of customer's intention to make a purchase decision and possible ways to develop the trust of customers on e-commerce service providers. This study also discusses the security related issues e. g. payment fraud, identity theft, its impact on the development and growth of e-commerce, and the significance of delivering secure communication ways to fascinate and successfully maintain a large customer base. It additionally discusses the privacy related issues of Pakistani customers in e-commerce and the significance of solid privacy frameworks that guarantee the security of customer's personal information. Conclusively, this study was developed to encourage further development and growth of e-commerce in Pakistan. The existing consumer protection laws in Pakistan do not contain specific provisions for addressing concerns of consumers transacting in digital environment but now according to the new e-commerce policy framework of Pakistan, recommendations have been made for introducing specific amendments in these laws. E-commerce in Pakistan witnessed an accelerated pace of growth over the period of the past few years with the sale value of the industry touching Rs. 100 billion so far. Pakistan is ranked at 120 among the different countries of the world, which is far behind the regional countries including China, India, Bangladesh, Nepal and etc. The issues related to e-commerce have been persistent despite an increase in its adopt-ability among the people and the consistent penetration in the coverage areas. The industry could move at a much faster pace if these issues are fixed on a long-term basis by the industry players and other stakeholders. In this study, the possible solutions given for the privacy, security, and trust related issues can be used by e-commerce organizations in Pakistan to boost the customers' confidence in performing online transactions. Unless and until e-commerce organizations

achieve the necessary delicate balance of privacy, security, and trust, effective and quantitative e-commerce

transactions in Pakistan will remain a problem.

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